

Exploring the Relationship Between Mouth Asymmetry and Speech-Language Disorders

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Author Note: This paper was written as part of an undergraduate research project. While it has undergone internal review and attempts to adhere to rigorous academic standards, readers are encouraged to approach its findings as part of early-stage, exploratory research.

Abstract:

This paper develops an extensive review of existing literature to examine how right-sided oromotor (mouth and facial motor) asymmetry correlates with speech and language processing in both neurotypical individuals and those with speech-language impairments. Based on studies of babies babbling (Holowka and Petitto, 2002), adults who stutter (Choo et al., 2010), a seven-year-old dysphasic brain dissection (Cohen et al., 1989), and neuroimaging of adults with specific language impairment (SLI) (Badcock et al., 2012), analysis suggests that abnormal lateralization of brain function and brain structure variation may manifest as atypical oromotor asymmetry during speech. While substantial research supports the left hemisphere's role in speech and language production (Berker, 1986; Manns, 2019), more extensive research is required to establish a stronger link between irregular manifestation of oromotor asymmetry being a result of abnormal brain structure. This paper suggests that research integrating neuroimaging with detailed oromotor assessments during speech, of both neurotypical and SLI-affected individuals would provide much more conclusive evidence regarding oromotor asymmetry variation indicating potential speech-language disorders.

Methodology

Sources were found using the Google Scholar and APA PsycNet databases and PubMed for medical terms (e.g. Dysphasia definition), as well as cited sources within other sources. Key search terms included some of the following: "oromotor", "asymmetry", "hemisphere specialization", "SLI", "mouth asymmetry", "right asymmetry", "babbling", "babies". Studies were limited to articles published in accredited peer-reviewed journals such as *Neuropsychologia*. Some sources were originally written in a different language and in those circumstances, an official translation copy was cited (e.g. Berker (1986) is an official translation of Broca (1865)). Findings were synthesized based on evidence provided within the source and the conclusion/discussion sections provided as well as the methodology used and how that could affect results found, and legitimacy of the source. Within this paper, findings from across several different sources were compared based on the same criteria. Caution was used when cross-comparing various sources as majority of the evidence regarding the relationship of brain structure variation and mouth asymmetry is largely preliminary. Studies were also grouped by topic rather than methodology, though there are references to all major sources throughout the paper.

1. Hemisphere Specialization and Asymmetry

Hemisphere specialization (HS) refers to the asymmetric structure of the brain that causes certain cerebral processes to become lateralized across each hemisphere: speech processing in the left hemisphere (Berker, 1986), and emotional processing in the right (Gainotti, 2012) to note some prominent examples. For the case of speech production which is lateralised in the left-hemisphere, right side asymmetry of the mouth can be a direct result due to a higher frequency of nerve impulses from the left hemisphere than the right. (Berker, 1986; Manns, 2019). Furthermore, right asymmetry manifests during word list generation and rhyming which are also known as propositional tasks, which consists of spontaneous utterances that conveys specific meaning (Hamilton et al., 2010). This is a result of propositional tasks being processed predominantly through the Broca's area, located within the left frontal lobe (Berker, 1986; Graves, 1985; Graves and Landis, 1990). Why the asymmetry of the mouth appears on the right side of the mouth is because each hemisphere controls the opposite side of the face as well as other major body parts (Gardner, 1968). Further examples of the physical manifestation of function lateralization: Hand asymmetry appears to manifest during speech based on auditory input as both speech and non-speech sounds processed by the left and right hemispheres, respectively (Kimura, 1973a, 1973b). Direction of eye gaze during cognitive activity (Ehrlichman and Weinberger, 1978), and facial movement during emotional expression (Borod et al., 1981; Ekman et al., 1981; Sackeim and Gur, 1978). These examples are more clear indicators that hemisphere specialization can manifest physically based on other cognitive tasks.

The mouth within the study is the most promising indicator of cerebral specialization because it appears to provide detail of hemisphere specialization as seen in studies by Graves and Nicholls. Furthermore, the mouth specifically is what one could expect to articulate the most during speech given its role in speech production.

1.1. Visual Expression of Right-Side Asymmetry

It is possible that the right side of the mouth plays more of a role in day-to-day communication than the left: Two out of the three main categories of mouth asymmetry in Nicholls and Searle (2006) paper demonstrate that phenomenon: (1) Asymmetries in the speakers mouth, and (2) asymmetries in the visual expression of the speakers mouth (Nicholls and Searle, 2006).

- (1) The right side of the mouth opens further and faster than the left side during both verbal and non-verbal speech because the left hemisphere is responsible for both motor control of that area (oromotor control: Mouth motor function), and language processing. However, verbal speech is considered to be more reliable in terms of right oromotor asymmetry than non-verbal (Graves and Landis, 1990) especially during speech activities like spontaneous speech production, and reciting song lyrics. Despite this, non-verbal speech can demonstrate right oromotor asymmetry during non-verbal singing. Singing songs without lyrics still uses external articulators (Nicholls and Searle, 2006).
- (2) Right oromotor asymmetry is believed to play a key role in the visual and auditory expressivity of a speaker's speech. In a study by Graves and Potter (1988), participants were told to listen to people saying tongue twisters articulated with either the left or right side of the mouth. Many participants found the tongue twisters articulated by the right side of the mouth to be clearer, which could be because the right side of the mouth is able to articulate more than the left (Graves and Potter, 1988). However, Nicholls and Searle did not explicitly state neurological reasons for this conclusion. Nevertheless, one could connect that the greater articulation of the right side of the mouth could be cause by the increased neuromotor impulses from the left hemisphere as seen on Graves and Landis (1990) (Berker, 1986; Graves and Landis, 1990; Manns, 2019).

Lip reading is often seen as a tool for deaf people but is also a valuable tool for speech between hearing people when considering the McGurk effect (McGurk and Macdonald, 1976). For example, if what you heard does not line up with what you expected to hear from the shape of one's lips, you could potentially merge what you heard and the sound you expected (McGurk and Macdonald, 1976). If you heard the word /bɒg/, but it looks as if they said /dɒg/, you may misinterpret the sound in your head. An experiment using the McGurk effect was done by playing a video which

consisted of two sounds being played at the same time but showing only the articulation of the left side of the mouth for one sound, and the right side for the other in a video. Participants were then asked to choose which sound was most clear, and like (Graves and Potter, 1988), majority picked the sound depicted to come from the right side of the mouth (Campbell, 1986). This supports the idea that not only is the right side of the mouth more auditorily expressive as seen with tongue twisters (Graves and Potter, 1988), but visually expressive too by manner of greater articulation (Campbell, 1986).

What these two categories of mouth asymmetry could be interpreted as is that the left hemisphere plays a key role in speech production and perception. Left hemisphere specialization during speech is what causes the right side of the mouth to articulate further and faster which is what causes the right side of the mouth to be more visually and auditorily comprehensible than the left. Replicating this study on those with atypical oromotor asymmetry, as we will discuss further could show how the visual expression of speech could change with the variations of brain structure.

2. Oromotor Asymmetry by Demographic

Oromotor asymmetry can manifest differently depending on the type of speech task. For propositional tasks such as word-list generation and rhyming words, a lateralization index (LI) of $+0.93$ was calculated (Graves and Landis, 1990). $(L - R) / (L + R) = LI$ is the formula of the lateralization index, but the number used to calculate that figure are not found which does take away from its reliability. Furthermore, there is a discrepancy of LI between sexes. Men tend to score higher LI where women would score lower. For example, when describing images, women saw on average less mouth asymmetry than men because women's responses were more "amused" than men's (Graves et al., 1982). However, this discrepancy is not noticeable in babies, where a blanket LI for all 10 participants were calculated regardless of baby's sex (Holowka and Petitto, 2002). Holowka and Petitto's study were only on a small sample of 10 babies so though their results are important, they are limited. The discrepancy of sex related differences in Graves and Holowka's study could indicate a psychological development later in later brain development and not a result of underlying brain structure, but no reason is given.

2.1. Mouth Asymmetry in Adults

The following analysis is of neurotypical adults, and though they are referred to as "normal" in several studies cited below, they will be referred to as "neurotypical" in this paper. Furthermore, analysis on Graves et al. (1982) experiment one is limited due to a missing page from original source.

Of 196 subjects, 76% (150 out of 196) displayed right-side mouth asymmetry during bilabial production (Graves et al., 1982). What is more, linking back to Gardner (1968) and the idea of contralateral hemisphere control, it would explain both why right asymmetry of the mouth occurs in Graves study based on the evidence supporting language processing in the left hemisphere. No conclusive evidence within Graves et al. (1982) definitively confirms this idea, but its validity appears likely. However, Graves et al. (1982) was not able to state that the left hemisphere is speech dominant, only motor dominant. Further research could demonstrate how variation oromotor asymmetry during both propositional and non-propositional speech tasks could indicate a potential shift in hemispheric dominance.

Damage to the Wernicke's area would cause sentence content to become illegible but structure would remain completely intact, and there would be minimal effect on articulation. Damage to the Broca's area would result in a notable change in speech. Weakness in right side mouth muscles, dysarthria (Neuromotor disorder affecting speech articulation (Jayaraman and Das, 2025)), and inability to form coherent sentences. The left hemisphere processes not only speech, but language too where the right hemisphere has little involvement in processing propositional speech tasks (Berker, 1986; Graves and Landis, 1990). Additionally, 90% of right-handed and 70% of left-handed people affected by either lesion/disease (Berker, 1986), or injection of anesthetic (Rasmussen and Milner, 1977) was seen to develop symptoms of a damaged Broca's area just described. This observation, in relation to provided evidence of language localization provides a compelling argument for language processing in the left hemisphere and more specifically, the Broca's area.

Overall, based on Graves et al. and Berker, connection between left hemisphere specialization and speech-language production is not an unlikely theory. Though there is no conclusive evidence, examples of right-side asymmetry during word propositional tasks or brain structure variation and its effect on speech could link towards the theory of left hemisphere specialization of language, even without that conclusive evidence.

2.2. Mouth Asymmetry in Babies

In comparison to adults, there is less research published regarding the mouth asymmetry of babies, Holowka and Petitto (2002) study takes 10 babies and uses a simple laterality index to calculate which hemisphere was perceived to be more dominant in any given linguistic motor-based task.

Babies as young as five-twelve months old can show signs of right oromotor asymmetry whilst babbling (Holowka and Petitto, 2002), which based on previous evidence can be linked to left hemisphere specialization. Babbles in this context were defined as single syllable vocalisations that were syllabically organized (consonant – vowel, etc...) and reduplicated. Any other vocalisation that did not fit these criteria were considered Non

babbles. Laterization indexes (LI) were calculated from 150 randomly selected sections of babbles, non-babbles, and smiles. $LI = (R-L)/(R+L+E)$, where $R = Right\ Opening$, $L = Left\ Opening$, $E = Equal\ Opening$. The following scores were calculated from that formula (no individual values for each variable were provided in the source). $+0.88$ during babbling, -0.82 during spontaneous smiles, and -0.08 during non-babbles. (Holowka and Petitto, 2002). There is a noticeable difference in hemisphere specialisation when observing babbling and spontaneous smiles. Right mouth asymmetry was found for babbling, like adults in Graves and Landis (1990). Left side asymmetry was found during spontaneous smiles, and though there is not a direct link, it could be comparable to how women were observed to have less right asymmetry than men when describing pictures (Graves et al., 1982). However, LI's calculated demonstrated that though babbles were seen as left-hemisphere dominant, since the LI for babbles was $+0.88$ and not higher, that could indicate bilateral speech processing, though this is only speculation.

Based on Holowka and Petitto (2002) some strong references can be made to similar studies of adults by Graves, Nicholls, etc which could indicate that babies as young as 5 months demonstrate cerebral hemisphere specialization. Despite that, it is important to note that the pool of subjects in this study was 10 (5 English and 5 French babies) babies, unlike Graves et al (1982) 196 adults. Further research on oromotor asymmetry in babies of a larger sample size would improve the validity of the results found in Holowka and Petitto (2002).

Theory could suggest that atypical mouth asymmetry in babies could potentially predict speech and language disorders that are not traditionally diagnosed until later stages in life. This topic is expanded on in sections (3) and (4).

2.3. A Variation of Mouth Asymmetry – Adults Who Stutter

Unfortunately there is very limited research on the potential of mouth asymmetry manifestation in people with SLI, so comparisons of different types of lip asymmetry found in adults who stutter (Choo et al., 2010) can be compared to brain scan results of adults with SLI (Badcock et al., 2012) to compare EMG results with white and grey matter of adults with SLI to make a prediction of how oromotor asymmetry could manifest in adults with SLI.

Choo et al. (2010) hypothesized that EMG results for adults who stutter (AS) would show right hemisphere dominance of speech processing and oromotor asymmetry that manifests on the left side of the mouth. Adults who do not stutter (ANS), in line with (Graves and Landis, 1990) were predicted to demonstrate expected left hemisphere dominance of speech processing and oromotor asymmetry of the right side of the mouth. Choo et al. (2010) focused on the bottom lips as they are the most active during speech. Adult stutters (AS) (ranging from mild – severe stuttering) and 5 Adult non-stutters (ANS) were used for comparison. All participants were self-reported to not have any neurological or health

condition and all 10 participants are right-handed. Asymmetry was based on lip muscle activity shown by EMG results which were used to measure oromotor activity. Results found demonstrated what was predicted in the hypothesis. AS demonstrated greater right-hemisphere involvement than ANS, as well as left-sided lower lip asymmetry. It was discussed that several factors could have caused the variation of lip asymmetry. AS could reflect a poor connection between the left hemisphere and the right side of the mouth. Speculation was also shown that timing differences in cerebral activation could be a cause as in ANS, the left hemisphere is often seen activating before the right (Palolahti et al., 2005; Saarinen et al., 2006). There was also the discussion of variation in muscle strength of the mouth, though there does not seem to be as much strength in this argument. Overall, there does seem to be a neurological difference between both AS and ANS that causes hemisphere dominance to shift.

Choo et al. (2010)'s results are significant but limited because they show a high tendency that oromotor asymmetry will change/vary based on brain structure variation without using neuroimaging software, which would show more conclusive evidence. Studies from the likes of Graves, Nicholls, etc use neurotypical participants, so results are consistent and comparable. Furthermore, stuttering is not a language disorder, but a neuromotor disorder, so making connections to language is complicated because they are seen as two separate systems. However, with sources on brain dissections of a dysphasic brain and neuroimaging of adults with SLI, a case can begin being built connecting language and speech.

3. Brain Structure Variation and its Effects

Looking previous studies of hemisphere specialization and their manifestation in oromotor asymmetry, only so much evidence can be provided to support the initial theory of the relationship between oromotor asymmetry and language disorders. However, there appears to be a lack of research regarding the idea of predicting speech and language disorders based of mouth asymmetry. Using a dysphasic brain dissection and study of SLI brain structure, the aim of this paper is to make a supportive argument of the further research. Further research regarding brain structure, nerve impulses, and oromotor asymmetry with speech and language disorders in mind would contribute to much more conclusive evidence. The following sections bring the established idea of hemisphere specialization and mouth asymmetry one step further connecting it to real life examples brain structure variation and its effect on oromotor asymmetry, as well as applications in a real language disorder, SLI.

3.1. Case Study of Dysphasia Patient

Although the primary focus of this paper is oromotor asymmetry, it is important to note that manifestation of asymmetry in motor function is not confined solely to the mouth, as mentioned in (1.2). Below is a case study regarding the dissection of a 7-year-old white girls' brain, who suffered from dysphasia (Cohen et al., 1989).

An initial neurological examination (at 3 years and 2 months of age) revealed asymmetric muscle stretch reflex 2+ on the right, within normal limits, and 3-4+ on the left side, demonstrating a stronger reflex on the left side of her body. Subsequent neurological examinations did not see a replication of this finding. Despite that, even a single instance of neuropathological symptoms such as asymmetric muscle reflex offers valuable insight into cognitive functions. Even temporary deviations of motor asymmetry could be reflective of underlying developmental variations in brain structure. Although this evidence is not conclusive of speech and language disorders manifesting in oromotor or other neuromotor functions of the body, it provides a potential indicator for further research into whether similar temporary manifestations could be linked to brain structure variation.

Figure (1) shows glial scarring caused by dysplastic microgyrus in the left insular cortex. Cohen et al. (1989) argues that this was a result of disturbance in neuronal migration assembly. In simpler terms, when neurons were migrating into cortical layers, something did not go right. and similar cases have been observed in people with dyslexia. Cohen et al., (1989) goes on to suggest that this abnormal development may be related to oromotor apraxia, anomia, and reliance on gesture. However, though Cohen et al., (1989) did imply this connection, the study does not establish a direct link between the glial scarring and impairments as mentioned before. However, this could demonstrate the correlation between cortical structure variation and oromotor function as we can see a possible direct relation between structure and oromotor variation.

Figure 1: Detail of the dysplastic gyrus. (Luxol fast blue-periodic acid-Schiff stain, x 80 before 52% reduction.) – (Cohen et al., 1989)

Findings from Cohen et al. (1989) are thought to show results of a strong connection between brain structure and manifestation in the mouth with oromotor apraxia. Emphasis should still be made that this was a single individual with other health related issues. Though findings from Cohen et al. (1989) does contribute to previous ideas of oromotor asymmetry variation in speech and language disorders, there is not enough data to act as conclusive evidence; there is only data from one individual. However, connections made between brain structure variation and oromotor apraxia are strong indicators that based on atypical oromotor asymmetry, could indicate underlying abnormal brain structure, speech, or language disorders. Further research should be done, potentially on living patients to see a real-life correlation between brain structure variation and its effect on oromotor asymmetry. Overall, evidence from

Cohen et al. (1989) does seem to suggest that variation in brain structure manifest in oromotor asymmetry, glial scarring within the left insular cortex could potential be linked to motor functions such as oromotor apraxia, anomia, and reliance on gesture.

3.2. Brain Structure of Adults with SLI

Due to abnormal brain structure of adults with specific language impairment (SLI), irregular hemisphere specialization in cognitive tasks could be expected (Badcock et al., 2012). Badcock et al. (2012) used voxel-bases morphometry (VBM) protocol, a statistical device used to measure differences in brain concentration, on fMRI scans of participants brains. It was found that adults with SLI have increased grey matter in the left inferior frontal region but reduced activation (Badcock et al., 2012). Furthermore, altered patterns of grey matter in the temporal areas and the caudate nucleus. These areas are essential for the planning and execution of speech. Mapping out grey matter is essential to one day associating grey matter variation to oromotor asymmetry variation. Making this connection could mean being able to predict SLI in younger individuals (assuming grey matter is consistent across age groups). However, that is only speculation and needs more conclusive evidence to support its validity. The findings in Badcock et al., (2012) are consistent with the observed speech production difficulties and oromotor control issues that individuals with SLI have. Based on the notion that individuals with SLI have reduced activation in the frontal left hemisphere of the brain and the idea that individuals with SLI exhibit speech difficulties, there seems to be a strong connection between variation of brain structure and how that manifests through mouth asymmetry.

Though Badcock et al. (2012)'s research was robust, their paper was theoretical in that it did not seem to apply the findings from neuroimaging to real life applications of people with SLI. Due to this, like Cohen et al (1989), evidence is not conclusive, and it merely acts as a support validating the research potential of the theory one could predict speech and language disorders based on oromotor asymmetry.

Further research is using similar techniques of neuroimaging used in Badcock et al. (2012) in correlation to oromotor asymmetry assessments of participants could create a much stronger connection between brain structure variation and oromotor asymmetry. This more conclusive evidence could act as a foundation to studying how accurately one's speech-language disorder could be predicted based on oromotor asymmetry. With these in mind, Badcock et al (2012) is still critical in supporting the idea that variation of brain structure could potentially affect mouth asymmetry during speech production.

4. Conclusion: How Brain Structure Variations Influences Mouth Asymmetry

In summary, the evidence presented in this paper suggest a critical role of hemispheric specialization and its manifestation in oromotor asymmetry, during speech and language production. The left-hemisphere, which has been well for processing speech and language faster than the right (Berker, 1986; Palolahti et al., 2005; Saarinen et al., 2006) is what could be the cause of observable right-side asymmetry of the mouth. This phenomenon is what could have caused the right-side asymmetry during propositional tasks in Graves and Landis (1990) where linguistic function of said tasks is widely believed to be left hemisphere dominant, through the Broca's area. Asymmetry is further supported by non-verbal motor tasks, where similar asymmetry was found in hand, eye, and facial movement.

Moreover, the oromotor asymmetry across demographics such as similarity of lateralization between adults and babies further supports the existence of cerebral specialization of speech and language in early development. Research into adults who stutter, a dysphasic brain dissection, and SLI brain structure further suggest that variation in brain structure may indeed influence oromotor asymmetry, potentially serving as an early indicator for speech and language disorders.

While these findings establish a solid foundation for justifying further research regarding brain structure variation and its effect on oromotor asymmetry, the current body of evidence remains preliminary. Future studies with neuroimaging techniques alongside oromotor assessments are essential to conclusively establishing a relationship between brain structure variations and mouth symmetry. Research within this field is critical because if being able to predict speech and language disorders based on oromotor asymmetry is established, this could potentially be extrapolated to infants, like those in Holowka and Petitto (2002). Their study already suggest that infants aged five to twelve months develop hemisphere specialization of speech and language based on lip asymmetry. With that connection in mind, speech and language disorders could be predicted earlier than ages they are currently diagnosed at now.

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